

Upgrade of the TRANSURANUS burnup module for the calculation of LFR fuel rods

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ABSTRACT

Fuel performance codes such as TRANSURANUS play an important role in the nuclear industry to ensure safety and optimization of the thermo-mechanical fuel pin design. The TRANSURANUS burnup module, i.e. TUBRNP, calculates the fuel inventory over time yielding radial distributions of the number densities of different isotopes in the fuel pin. This information is essential for reproducing several physical phenomena like swelling, fission gas release and actinide redistribution. Existing versions of TRANSURANUS did not fully support lead-cooled fast reactors (LFRs). This work fills this gap for what concerns the burnup and the fuel inventory calculations. A methodology for future TUBRNP extensions is proposed and implemented through Monte Carlo codes like Serpent and OpenMC, as well as the deterministic code DRAGON5. The results of these different codes are shown to be compatible, with OpenMC results used to extend the burnup module. Additionally, DRAGON5 calculations show that the LFR cross sections are nearly burnup-independent, but sensitive to the leakage model adopted.

Keywords: Fuel performance, LFR, cross-section preparation, burnup, neutron transport

1. INTRODUCTION

Fuel performance is indispensable for the development of new reactor technologies. Advanced reactors often employ innovative materials and operate under new physical conditions for which limited experimental data exist. Fuel performance codes are fundamental for predicting the thermo-mechanical behaviour of the fuel rod during irradiation as they simulate key phenomena like fuel swelling, fission gas release, and fuel-cladding interaction. This predictive capability is important for several reasons:

- Safety & Licensing, to demonstrate fuel integrity under normal, incident and accident conditions, forming the basis of the safety case for regulatory approval;
- Design Optimization of fuel and cladding, to maximize performance, increase burnup, and enhance economic viability;
- R&D Guidance, to identify potential failure mechanisms and guide experimental programs.

The TRANSURANUS (TU) code is the tool adopted for fuel performance studies for the design of *newcleo* LFRs [1, 2]. TU is developed by the European Commission Joint Research Center (JRC). Fast calculations are made possible by the simplified '1.5D' model where the fuel rod is divided into separate axial slices. After that, the slices must be coupled together so that quantities such as the inner pin pressure or the axial friction forces between fuel and cladding can be determined [3].

Despite the wide range of available fuel pin types, the TU burnup model, i.e. TUBRNP, does not have specific LFR nuclear data. This work focuses on the TUBRNP extension for LFR applications with a new set of homogenized cross sections. A brief presentation of TUBRNP is provided in Section 2; Section 3 gives an overview of the methodology followed to generate the cross section dataset and the tools to implement it: two Monte Carlo codes, i.e. OpenMC (version 0.15.0) [4] and Serpent (version 2.2.1) [5], and a deterministic lattice code DRAGON5 (version 5.0.11) [6]. Results from these codes are compared in Section 4, and the impact of depletion and the leakage model is investigated. Finally, Section 5 proposes future perspectives for this work together with the conclusions.

2. OVERVIEW OF THE TUBRNP MODULE

Fuel utilization under irradiation is characterized by the burnup variable, i.e. the amount of energy that has been released by nuclear reactions per unit of heavy metal in the fuel. Two burnup models are available in TU [7]: RADAR (“RAting Depression Analysis Routine”) and TUBRNP. The latter was developed to overcome the limitations of the former in treating high-burnup and MOX fuel.

TUBRNP computes the thermal power radial profile of each pin slice at each timestep. It receives at input the initial radial concentrations of actinides; then, from their respective capture and fission cross sections stored in the *XSecTbl.f95* subroutine, it solves a system of Bateman equations for each node. Then, the updated fissile actinide radial concentrations are used in *FpYield_fast.f95* subroutine as weights in the computation of the overall yield of each fission product, i.e. Cs, Nd, Kr and Xe [3].

As previously said, before this work TUBRNP did not have an LFR cross section dataset. The alternatives were either to use the data for a sodium fast reactor or to do without TUBRNP, i.e. imposing a radial power density profile per each axial slice through external files. With the improvements in this work, TUBRNP has been updated to LFRs, so that the Pu, Am and He concentrations are calculated consistently allowing users to [3]:

- affect modules *Puredi* and *Amredi*, responsible for Pu and Am redistributions and for constraints on the maximum T_{fuel} ;
- produce He, which is needed for the fuel swelling modelling in *FISPRO* module.

The LFR cross sections are therefore necessary to simulate the fuel depletion according to a physics-based best estimate approach.

3. METHODOLOGY

The highest thermal and mechanical stresses are often the focus of fuel performance studies. A representative fuel rod is chosen to reproduce assumed operating conditions, which can be penalized on demand to emphasize the underlying physical phenomena until compromising safety functions like cladding integrity. Homogenised cross sections for TUBRNP are prepared in a 2D-like fuel pin cell problem using reflective boundary conditions (BCs) creating an infinite lattice environment. Section 4.2.1 will study the influence of a leakage model used for DRAGON5 calculations.

For the generic reaction x and nuclide n , the microscopic cross section $\bar{\sigma}_{x,n}$ is computed as the ratio:

$$\bar{\sigma}_{x,n} = \frac{\int_{V_{fuel}} d^3r \int_0^{\infty} dE \phi(\vec{r}, E) \sigma_{x,n}(E)}{\int_{V_{fuel}} d^3r \int_0^{\infty} dE \phi(\vec{r}, E)}, \quad (1)$$

where $\phi(\vec{r}, E)$ is the scalar neutron flux that is function of space \vec{r} and neutron energy E . Each cross section is assumed to be spatially uniform in the fuel. In TUBRNP, the presence of the ‘rim effect’ [8] in LWRs is reproduced by using uniform cross sections in the pin, but recurring to a Helmholtz diffusion equation for the neutron flux form function and to empirical correction functions for resonant capture at the outer pellet, thus yielding peaked power density at the fuel periphery. The rim effect is not present in fast reactors where the mean free path is much longer than the lattice cell pitch.

Cross sections are assumed to be constant during irradiation. Possible variations of cross sections from this constant behavior in time are investigated in Section 4.2.2. The integrals in (1) are restricted to the fuel volume V_{fuel} for the following set of reactions:

- fission (MT=18) and capture (MT=102) for the following isotopes: ^{232}Th , ^{233}Th , ^{231}Pa , ^{233}Pa , ^{232}U , ^{233}U , ^{234}U , ^{235}U , ^{236}U , ^{237}U , ^{238}U , ^{239}U , ^{237}Np , ^{238}Np , ^{239}Np , ^{238}Pu , ^{239}Pu , ^{240}Pu , ^{241}Pu , ^{242}Pu , ^{243}Pu , ^{241}Am , ^{242}Am , ^{243}Am , ^{244}Am , ^{242}Cm , ^{243}Cm , ^{244}Cm , ^{245}Cm .
- α particle production reaction for only ^{16}O

These cross sections extend the number of datasets in the *XSecTbl.f95* subroutine of TUBRNP by adopting ENDF/B-VIII.0 [9] as nuclear data library.

The α particle production involves radioactive decay plus different neutron-induced reactions. As an example, those concerning ^{16}O in the ENDF/B-VIII.0 library are $(n, n\alpha)$, $(n, n3\alpha)$, $(n, np\alpha)$, (n, α) , $(n, 2\alpha)$ and $(n, p\alpha)$ reactions with MT numbers 22, 23, 45, 107, 108, 112, respectively. Due to null responses in both OpenMC and Serpent for ^{16}O MT=45 and MT=112 reactions, the α particle production is limited to the combination $(MT = 22) + 3 \cdot (MT = 23) + (MT = 107) + 2 \cdot (MT = 108)$, which takes into account the multiplicity of the emitted α particles.

3.1. OpenMC & Serpent

Monte Carlo calculations are performed using 970 active and 30 inactive batches and 7000 particles per batch. These parameters ensure cross section generations with relative standard deviations below 0.1% for every nuclide. All calculations are performed in continuous energy mode and with fresh fuel. Monte Carlo modeling of neutron transport is considered as a reference since it is more accurate because of fewer approximations in calculations. After successful comparison of OpenMC cross sections with those produced by Serpent, the OpenMC output can be used as the reference dataset.

3.2. DRAGON5

DRAGON5 is a lattice code designed for the solution of the multigroup neutron transport balance equation. Its structure is modular, with each calculation module handling a specific task and exchanging information through the Ganlib driver [6]. In this study, multigroup nuclear data are based on the ENDF/B-VIII.0 library, using a 1962-group structure for cross sections, while the depletion chain is derived from the 315-group SHEMA315 library. The geometry is defined as a hexagonal cell composed of multiple cylindrical fuel regions, radially subdivided into three zones (50%, 30%, and 20% of the fuel volume) to achieve a detailed spatial mesh. Reflective BCs are imposed at the cell boundary. Tracking data are used to implement the Method of Characteristics (MOC) for neutron flux calculation, while self-shielded microscopic cross sections are obtained from the Tone's method, an heterogeneous-homogeneous equivalence principle dedicated to fast spectrum lattices. The transport equation is solved with (TYPE B) or without (TYPE K) taking leakage into account, and the results are finally condensed and homogenized over the fuel volume.

In this work, DRAGON5 is used because it can explicitly model fundamental mode condition through a leakage model, which is not available in OpenMC. Moreover, it allows performing burnup-dependent calculations with significantly lower computational cost, making it suitable for generating cross sections that include both leakage and depletion effects efficiently.

4. RESULTS

Due to the differences among stochastic and deterministic codes, the evaluation of the quality of the result must take into account the nature of these two approaches. Hence, the results of the two Monte Carlo codes are compared to each other with a statistical test, and those from DRAGON5 are evaluated with OpenMC outputs as reference values.

The cross section dataset feeding *XSecTbl.f95* is reported in Table II and is computed with DRAGON5 by implementing a leakage model, which is presented in Section 4.2.1.

4.1. OpenMC & Serpent results

This section presents the results of both Monte Carlo simulations for the reactions of interest in Table I and in Figure 1. Cross sections of U-239, Th-233 and Am-244 are not part of the DRAGON5 library, so N is reduced to 53.

Table I. Descriptive parameters for the distribution of $\delta = \frac{|\sigma_{\text{ENDF/B-VIII.0}} - \sigma_{\text{JEFF-3.3}}|}{\sigma_{\text{ENDF/B-VIII.0}}} \cdot 100$

N	avg	max	min	p25	p50	p75
59	10.05	158.87	0.06	0.87	1.56	7.34

Table II. DRAGON5 results with ENDF/B-VIII.0 and leakage model

Isotope	Fission σ_f [b]	Capture σ_c [b]
Th-232	0.0090	0.3643
Th-233	-	-
Pa-231	0.1754	1.3851
Pa-233	0.0311	1.5110
U-232	1.6105	0.4735
U-233	2.6076	0.2502
U-234	0.3158	0.4348
U-235	1.8288	0.5070
U-236	0.0931	0.4134
U-237	0.6124	0.4237
U-238	0.0387	0.2640
U-239	-	-
Np-237	0.3338	1.4966
Np-238	2.5220	0.3451
Np-239	0.0854	1.0832
Pu-238	1.0650	0.5888
Pu-239	1.7384	0.4470
Pu-240	0.3745	0.4590
Pu-241	2.3956	0.4058
Pu-242	0.2628	0.3904
Pu-243	0.7432	0.3273
Am-241	0.2564	1.7607
Am-242	3.0127	0.3725
Am-243	0.1877	1.5721
Am-244	-	-
Cm-242	0.6937	0.7359
Cm-243	3.2209	0.3332
Cm-244	0.4704	0.5617
Cm-245	2.5563	0.4086
O-16	α production [b]	
MT=22	-	-
MT=23	-	-
MT=107	9.140E-4	
MT=108	1.340E-10	
SUM	9.140E-4	

Figure 1. Welch-t-Test results depicted as dartboard points: the angular distribution is random and the distance $Q = \frac{(\bar{X}_{\text{OMC}} - \bar{X}_{\text{SERP}})}{\sqrt{\sigma_{\bar{X}_{\text{OMC}}}^2 + \sigma_{\bar{X}_{\text{SERP}}}^2}}$ from the center must be within the limit circle with radius 3 to pass the test

Quality assessments of the results from different stochastic codes have to include uncertainties. For a given cross section, the results are normally distributed, with a mean value \bar{X} and a variance $\sigma_{\bar{X}}$ which are different for each code, i.e. $(\bar{X}_{\text{OMC}}, \sigma_{\bar{X}_{\text{OMC}}})$ and $(\bar{X}_{\text{SERP}}, \sigma_{\bar{X}_{\text{SERP}}})$. To compare each couple of results, a Welch-*t*-test is performed [10]. This tests if the two distributions have equal means. It consists in evaluating the ratio $Q = (\bar{X}_{\text{OMC}} - \bar{X}_{\text{SERP}}) / \sqrt{\sigma_{\bar{X}_{\text{OMC}}}^2 + \sigma_{\bar{X}_{\text{SERP}}}^2}$, where $(\bar{X}_{\text{OMC}} - \bar{X}_{\text{SERP}})$ is the difference of the mean values, with standard deviation $\sqrt{\sigma_{\bar{X}_{\text{OMC}}}^2 + \sigma_{\bar{X}_{\text{SERP}}}^2}$. The absolute value of Q must be less than 3 to pass the test. It can be demonstrated that the difference of these two normally distributed random variables has a Gaussian distribution as well and, as a consequence of the Central Limit Theorem, that $Pr[Q \leq n] \approx 99.7\%$ for $n = 3$.

The Welch-*t*-test is passed by each cross-section, as exhibited in Figure 1. The farthest points from the circle center are high-energy threshold reactions with poor statistics, such as fission of ^{233}Pa or $(n, 3\alpha)$ of ^{16}O . Other 'high' Q values might be explained by a combination of factors, such as different Doppler broadening treatment and the flux estimator, as well as statistical fluctuations inherent to Monte Carlo simulations. In general, the OpenMC results are qualitatively comparable to those of Serpent. The variability between the use in Serpent of ENDF/B-VIII.0 and JEFF-3.3 [11] is quantified with the relative discrepancy $\delta = \frac{|\sigma_{\text{ENDF/B-VIII.0}} - \sigma_{\text{JEFF-3.3}}|}{\sigma_{\text{ENDF/B-VIII.0}}} \cdot 100$ in Table I, where N is the total number cross sections, while *avg*, *max* and *min* stand for the average, the maximum and the minimum value of discrepancies respectively. p_{25} , p_{50} and p_{75} indicate the 25-th, the 50-th and the 75-th distribution percentiles respectively. 75% of the discrepancies are below 7.34%, but relevant peak values can be observed: they refer to reactions with negligible contribution to the macroscopic cross section, such as fission of ^{238}Np (34.75%) or capture of ^{237}U (158.87%). However, the combined impact of these discrepancies should not be neglected. Indeed, preliminary analyses of TU simulations have shown that using different cross section datasets, characterized by a discrepancy distribution similar to that of Table I, results in relative variations in nuclide radial distributions that can reach up to 20%. Table I points out the importance of clearly referencing the adopted library for *XSecTbl.f95* datasets for future reproducibility tests.

4.2. DRAGON5 results

In a similar way as done in Table I, this section presents DRAGON5 results along with the relative error $\frac{\sigma_{\text{DRG}} - \sigma_{\text{OMC}}}{\sigma_{\text{OMC}}} \cdot 100$ with respect to OpenMC without any leakage model (investigated in Section 4.2.1). As shown in Table III with the values on the first row, the highest discrepancies reach approximately 0.03% (in absolute value 0.64%). However, significant errors have been verified to occur only for isotopes that contribute less than 1% to the total macroscopic fission or capture cross sections. Table III illustrates the consistency between the two codes, proving that DRAGON5 agrees well with Monte Carlo codes for this task.

The calculations were performed using a fine 1962-group energy library, allowing for an accurate representation of the fast neutron spectrum typical of LFRs and other fast reactor systems. The excellent agreement observed between DRAGON5 and OpenMC therefore confirms that the adopted multigroup structure is well suited for the present analysis and supports the reliability of the deterministic approach when an appropriately detailed energy library is employed.

4.2.1. Leakage model

Up to this point, neutron fluxes are the solutions of a supercritical configuration due to fresh fuel and reflective BCs which result in a $k_{\text{eff}} = 1.19739 \pm 0.00023$ for the OpenMC simulation and 1.19820 for DRAGON5. In such a set-up, the spectrum may differ from that actually experienced by the pins in the critical configuration. Leakage models artificially emulate neutron losses that would occur in a real, finite system, either in the axial or radial directions, by introducing a dummy absorption term that re-

Table III. Descriptive parameters of distribution of relative errors $\frac{\sigma_{\text{DRG}} - \sigma_{\text{OMC}}}{\sigma_{\text{OMC}}} \cdot 100$ caused by using DRAGON5 instead of OpenMC without leakage model (Top); Descriptive parameters of distribution of relative errors $\frac{\sigma_{\text{LEAK}} - \sigma_{\text{NOLEAK}}}{\sigma_{\text{NOLEAK}}} \cdot 100$ caused by using DRAGON5 with leakage model instead of the case without it (Bottom)

	N	avg	max	min	p25	p50	p75
DRG vs OMC	53	-0.24	0.03	-0.64	-0.34	-0.26	-0.12
LEAK vs NOLEAK	53	-0.71	17.27	-10.07	-7.48	-4.18	8.94

produces the effect of neutron leakage not explicitly treated by the BCs and allows the reproduction of a fundamental mode operation through the B1 approximation. The flux is computed as a results of a so-called critical buckling-search calculation, i.e. dummy absorptions are iteratively updated until the criticality of the system is reached [12]. The resulting flux will be a better estimate of the one actually experienced by the pin, and will thus allow a better energy condensation of cross sections. Table III schematically reports the distributions of relative errors $\frac{\sigma_{\text{LEAK}} - \sigma_{\text{NOLEAK}}}{\sigma_{\text{LEAK}}} \cdot 100$ between cross sections computed by using a buckling search calculation and without leakage model. The distribution of relative errors is compared with that discussed in Section 4.2.

Table III relative errors of the second row reach about 17.27% between the cross sections of the condensed one group with the two fluxes. The discrepancies are found even for the most important reactions such as capture and fission of uranium and plutonium isotopes. This outcome highlights that the flux computed under reflective conditions (i.e. infinite medium) differs significantly from that corresponding to a critical configuration. By accounting for neutron leakage through the buckling search, the deterministic solution becomes more representative of the pin environment within the reactor lattice. This justifies the adoption of DRAGON5 cross section dataset in TU.

4.2.2. Burnup calculation

The evaluated one-group averaged cross sections could vary with burnup, as many LWR datasets in *XSecTbl.f95* can attest. In this analysis, a series of burnup calculations are performed to assess whether neutron cross sections vary significantly throughout the fuel cycle. These calculations are performed using the *EV0*: module within DRAGON5. This module solves the Bateman equations by employing adaptive Runge-Kutta methods, specifically the Cash-Karp and Kaps-Rentrop schemes, to achieve both numerical accuracy and computational efficiency [6, 12].

For this analysis, the time integration in *EV0*: is configured using a nonuniform temporal mesh, defined by the time points up to 1600 days and by the cumulative burnup values up to 62.6 MWd/kgHM. To quantify the variation, the relative mean discrepancy is calculated for each isotope and reaction type, defined as the ratio of the standard deviation divided by the mean, i.e. $\frac{std}{\bar{\sigma}}$. The mean value of each cross section is calculated as the arithmetic average of its values at all burnup steps throughout the simulation. The standard deviation is then computed with respect to this mean, using the usual unbiased estimator over the same set of burnup points.

Figures 2-3 exhibit $\frac{std}{\bar{\sigma}}$ for the fuel nuclides, both with the leakage model and without it. As shown, the relative mean discrepancy values remain low for the reactor types under investigation, with a maximum value of approximately 0.81% for ^{232}Th , whose contribution to macroscopic fission and capture rates is negligible. This indicates that, for this particular reactor configuration and fuel composition, the cross sections remain effectively constant throughout the burnup cycle. The small variation observed in the one-group cross sections with burnup implies that, for TU applications, it is sufficient to use burnup-independent values. This approach greatly simplifies the implementation by avoiding the introduction of burnup-dependent correlations for cross section adjustment, as done in other TU datasets.

Figure 2. Relative mean error of the fission cross section: in red are the results with the leakage model, in green those without it. Figure 3. Relative mean error of the capture cross section: in red are the results with the leakage model, in green those without it.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This work has provided a new set of microscopic cross sections from OpenMC in TUBRNP to be used in LFR applications. The calculation of the cross sections with OpenMC, Serpent and DRAGON5 has shown good agreement among these three codes for the same input parameters. The fuel depletion does not significantly affect the weighting neutron spectrum, so the cross sections can be considered as burnup-independent. These additions to TU make analyses of LFR fuel pins more complete by including Pu and Am redistribution and He production in calculations. In this extension of cross section datasets for LFR applications, the adopted library and system configuration are reported in the comments, a practice that should be adopted for future extensions to guarantee the compliance of the new cross sections with existing ones and their reproducibility.

In the future, DRAGON5 results with leakage will be checked in TU and implemented in TUBRNP. It might also be interesting to expand this analysis to a full-core configuration to compare the results of the most realistic model with those already computed. This will be done to further justify the assumption of a single pin and constant cross sections. Finally, TU calculations for LFRs will be performed to check the influence of different assumptions and data libraries in fuel performance studies: comparisons of nuclide densities for the most important actinides calculated by DRAGON5 and TU along a burnup

calculation will be shown in a future work, thus completing the verification of the implementation in TU.

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